

THE APPLICABILITY OF LAW 10.639/2003 AND THE TEACHING PRAXIS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the applicability of Law 10.639/03 in student learning about African history and culture. Its scientific relevance lies in expanding research around teaching on this topic, which has become mandatory in the Brazilian educational network. Its objective is to carry out an analysis of Law 10.639/2003 and what can be achieved through teaching praxis. It is a bibliographical research. The obstacle to teaching African history and culture is the philosophical, sociological, phenomenological, epistemological and empirical unpreparedness of those who teach the contents, which leads, as a consequence, to distorted learning about the target object of systematic studies. Education should face the teaching of Africanity in schools as culture; not as a favor or something you are obligated to fulfill on the calendar. Slavery should cease to be inherent in the waste of humanity, as no one is a slave; people were, and still are, in many cases, enslaved. The term slave naturalizes the condition of people having the pessimistic, pejorative and prejudiced idea that, unfortunately, was being built during the history of mankind. The teaching of Afro culture in most schools is still related to slavery and suffering, having the impression that history has not evolved in conquests and achievements, positive contributions to the social construction of the nation. The stories told in most schools are mostly research related to the aspect of suffering, pain or, in a way, without the slightest preparation to discuss religions of African origin, passing, with this, aspects of negativity.

Keywords: Afro-Brazilian culture; Federal Law n. 10,639/03; Education.

INTRODUCTION

Brazil since the enactment of the Federal Constitution of 1988, in which it listed in its guidelines, citizenship as the most valuable and sovereign asset, considered as instrument odd for O development Social of the Brazilians puttingThe education as cornerstone necessary for such. Although, in this to the what tange you parameters curriculum national It is to the guidelines Educational there was one lack of real cultural historical support for the appreciation of African culture in Brazil. The heroic history of pride and performance of the people of origin African were camouflaged in our schools that today through research in anthropological and social resistances we perceive the real origin and race of heroes from the history what they were black, however, The history hid your true ethnic.

The stories reported in social studies from the 1970s to the 1980s, in Brazil at the talk about the history of Africa and its ethnicities and everything that involves the world African we remember the time of the late 1980s and early 1990s of the school from the network public whose stories related The culture african ever they were linked to slavery or some other kind of suffering, prisons, inequality, inferiority, with the feeling that abolition was a favor that our Portuguese patriarchs had with the newcomers individuals from the continent African what at era (16th/17th century) now colonized to the Brazil.

The question raised around primary school *literary memories in* around the ideological construction of blacks in Brazil we perceive from the studies social movements of the 1980s coupled with the teachings of moral and civic education and the social studies sayings or dates that only recalled the abolition of slavery even though the country is going through a period of attempts at meekness and cohesion of the population with a view to creating a new school, with the aim of studying social with projects offered by the military for direct The population current.

In this sense, there is what,

The school was used to disseminate desirable values and maintain 'peaceful' society, despite the liberal and New School rhetoric that defended to the freedoms individual. For in addition of that rhetoric, the 'basements from the dictatorship' shut up who no agreed with to the impositions of regime military. A emphasis us Studies Social translated what knowledge would be taught in schools, fulfilling a very important role, which is: to break the social resistance, via a curriculum full of moral values It is ethical, thought for The training of citizen (JACOMELI, 2016, P. 76) [*Italics in original*]

A education moral It is civic gift at the curriculum offered at the Brazil in the decades from 1970 to 1990 was intended to teach values and training of individuals for one society

desired leaving imperceptible you black, you homosexuals, women with themes and methods derived from France, England, U.S It is Italy.

In this period, ethnic minorities, too, constituted a wide range of excluded who claimed their place in the country's social history. with the resume with cultures denied and silenced by heated speeches in the name of a [*said*] school curriculum. According to Gomes (2008), those excluded from speeches normative of curriculum school launched hand in strategies collective It is individuals, articulating themselves in networks, giving rise to various social movements in identity character.

O Brazil crossed a military period of spirit patriot with The sensation imposed of total nationality where the national culture was denied and camouflaged in the curriculum with decolonization in LDB nº 5692/1971. the constituent assembly that elaborated the LDB 9394/1996 had a gap leaving out, due to ignorance or for its own motivation the relevance of teaching the history of afro culture for humanistic psycho-intellectual and cognitive development of students at basic education. In LDB 9394/96 it was not a memory lapse, being excluded due to the fact that what who elaborated The educational law judged that was not, intellectually and humanistically relevant to formal student learning. In this sense, becomes imperative O emergence in one ordinance what inferat the thought brazilian educational, the topic about Africa and africanities.

A LAW 10.639/03

Law 10,639, enacted in 2003, establishes that establishments of primary and secondary education, official and private, education becomes mandatory on Afro-Brazilian History and Culture, with a view to highlighting and thus valuing “the struggle of the blacks in Brazil, the Brazilian black culture and the black in the formation of national society, rescuing the contribution of black people in the social, economic and political aspects relevant to the History of Brazil” (BRASIL, 2003, *sp* .), being the contents related to Afro-Brazilian History and Culture taught within the of the entire school curriculum, especially in the areas of Arts Education and Literature It is History Brazilian.

The country tries, with such an attitude, to soften what history has hidden for hundreds of years. years, keeping hidden from the nation Brazilian The true culture of the people of African descent, things that the country tries to alleviate, with a view to building a new paradigm of *equality*; correct mistakes made decades ago and still today It is unfortunately reposting wrong by the ours professionals from the education that leaves us with the impression

that the same story you heard in your infantile period in its infancy with ethnic racial histories intertwined only The slavery, cowardices, spells with stereotypes in inferiorities, low self-esteem, devaluation, racism, that everything was ended with the kindness of abolition hiding like this your real identity.

During This one time we gave O our shout in freedom [...] A freedom to be black, to dance our dance, to sing our song. This song tells our story and our deliverance. And this true song echoed in Curuzu: a song of faith for a better world. The brightness of the avenue does not dazzle the brilliance of this breed of Nagô origin (CADERNOS CANTO..., 1988, P. 32).

In this line we realize the importance of amending the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (Law 9394/96) through the sanction of Law nº 10.639/03 and its regulation by opinion CNE/CP 03/2004 and by resolution CNE/CP 01/2004 (BRAZIL, 2005) what awake in between you professionals from the education the responsibility of transmitting the appreciation of black culture seeking guidelines rich, fruitful and literary outlining in the systematic construction a discussion plausible It is cultural without etymological ruptures of start of our history.

One of the most important roles of education is training and development. physical, intellectual and moral of the human being. And among these, the role of education in societies contemporary, we would highlight, in this context specific introduction and marking of an education and school project for the country, which preparation (of the student) for the exercise of citizenship and his/her qualification for the work (BRASIL, 1996) could never be give, according to the words of Paulo Freire himself (2008) where he emphasizes that, without the experience or effort of understanding that characterizes the reading of the world. At least, without that sense bigger, no.

The education professional since the beginning of civilization with regard to posture of educator It is in respect or source primordial in mediator in knowledge. AND O cornerstone The figure what transmit security The mediation in learnings. In Brazil, the fertility of cultures that once we realized to the minister O teaching formal mixed to the knowledge informal.

rethinking The training of the teachers The leave from the analysis from the practice pedagogical, Pimenta identifies the emergence of the issue of knowledge as a aspects considered about the identity of the teacher's profession. Part of premise of what,

This identity is constructed from the social significance of profession; of the constant review of the social meanings of profession; of the revision of traditions. But also the reaffirmation of practices consecrated culturally It is what remain follow- beneficial. Practices that resist innovation because they

are pregnant with valid knowledge to the needs of reality. From the confrontation between to the theories It is to the practices, from the analysis systematic of practices The light of existing theories, the construction of new theories (PIMENTA,1999, p.19).

In this way, it rescues the importance of considering the teacher in his own training, in a process of self-training, of re-elaboration of initial knowledge in comparison with their lived practice. In this way, your knowledge will be constituted from a reflection on and about practice. This reflexive tendency introducing as one new paradigm at training in teachers, sedimenting one policy in development guys It is professional of the teachers It is of the institutions school.

Federal Law 10.639/03 instituted the 20th of November as National Day of Black Consciousness to which the dead quilombola leader refers and pays homage Palmares Zumbi. In 2008 the Law was amended by the Law 11.645/08 becomes mandatory teaching of Afro Culture in all public and private schools in the Elementary Education to Secondary Education. It was an act that was applauded and of great merit. enjoyment, hopefully wish your efficiency if no we were we bumped at decentralization of teacher training with regard to didactics and ways methodological, with the offer of education being mandatory in all schools; the critic discussed It is as This one teaching it is being offered in our schools considering the question that, if the professionals are, really, prepared for teaching Afro culture or are they just reproducing what they heard of teaching regular?

A PRAXIS PEDAGOGICAL RECURRENT ABOUT HISTORY AND CULTURE AFRO

O teaching from the culture Afro in the majorities of schools It is, yet, related The slavery It is Suffering having The print what The history no evolved in achievements It is achievements, contributions positive for The construction Social from thenation. To the stories counted at majority of schools in your majority are surveys related to aspects of suffering, pain or in a way without unprepared to discuss the religions passing aspect of negativity. Education professionals should pay attention to Afro-Brazilian culture as a constituent in contribution at training Brazilian you black as subjects historic. Although how to talk about something that in your school background juvenile or academic there was not? If the teaching of Afro culture in schools were just the from the year 2003 when the day of black conscience appeared even as a way of memory awareness in society, more and before 2003 what was taught in the schools? AND common It is custom yet today observe in the didactic offered the enhancement of history of slavery and suffering. If these teachers formed today in his childhood

only hear stories related to suffering and negativities will possibly continue to reproduce what you have learned since their school and academic education. Believing what he learned was the right, because it is in the history of Brazil. We can't change the past though, we can contribute with one gift different focused at appreciation. It is self-esteem cultural those who contributed, greatly, for the consolidation of sovereignty of Brazilian people.

The hidden wealth that engages the true history of the African people who we can find in literary research or often heard from the descendants who also heard it from their grandparents who also heard it from their grandparents. At happiness of relationship Social from the community, in the traditions religious, in music and dance, in cooking, poetry, that is, in its social culture as a whole. We have excellent characters who have marked our nation and what contributed for our social growth.

Education should face the teaching of Africanity in schools as culture; not as a favor or something you are obligated to fulfill on the calendar. A slavery should cease to be inherent in the waste of humanity, as no one is a slave; people were, and still are, in many cases, enslaved. The term slave naturalizes the condition of people having the idea pessimistic, pejorative. It is prejudiced that, unfortunately, it was being built during the story from the humanity.

An education needs invest at training in teachers, one turn what The teacher's identity is something that consolidates as his/her self matures and begins to accept that other ways of thinking that differ from theirs must be accepted. It is same presented to the your students as a way of to allow The training in legitimate autonomy.

Paulo Freire teaches that the educator not only builds an identity but also open opportunities to enlarge your knowledge, in the end,

Teaching is not transferring knowledge, content, nor training is action by which a creative subject gives form, style or soul to a indecisive and accommodated body. There is no teaching without teaching, the two explain each other and their subjects, despite the differences that they connote, they are not reduced to the condition of object, one of the other. Who teaches learn to the to teach. It is who learn teaches to the learn. Who teaches teaches something to someone (FREIRE, 2008, p.08).

Highlighting with this speech that the educator passes to the student *knowledge elaborate*, but between both (educator and student) there is a huge abyss. That reaches your student is information, this because its placement is permeated for the experience socio-cultural-economic so much own how much of student.

Federal Law n. 10.639/03 being respected and with character of aggregation of values to society and school contribute to a better future, because every being man must be prepared,

especially thanks to the education he receives in youth, to elaborate autonomous and critical thoughts and to formulate the your own value judgments so that you can decide for yourself how to act in different circumstances of life. The epistemological formation of the teacher he must to be conceived It is understood as one process in developmentprofessional, where The training initial It is continued constitute one chain coherent It is to be continued in development in knowledge, behaviors, skills, attitudes It is values what they go constituting The specificity of to be educator is that it happens during all The life of work.

It is a challenge for education to review its priorities in terms of culture, for the law is present for fulfillment and we know that there is a debt and years of negative labels of more than 100 (one hundred) years and does not erase from one year to another, but we have optimism and responsibility and ethics as professionals in education in bring equality cultural.

CONCLUSION

A education it needs discover as break up with The dichotomy existing in between machine school in reproduction of inequalities social It is school-place per excellence in combating these same inequalities. However, the school itself believes that without these social miseries, its function would be relegated to a void intellectual; so strong It is O inculcation in what The education formalized he can solve all the problems of world.

Brazil, with Law 10.69/03, tries to soften and correct years of inequalities that we still perceive through the unpreparedness of several professionals this gap to the which we realized what O teacher no search to obtain researches fruitfulrelated to reality, to the culture of our ancestors and preach disillusionment, suffering that was generated and inflicted on a culture, thus passing on the image of a race without esteem, ideals, without glory, repeating the illusion of a freedom paper, but reviewing the eternal slavery of social inequality. The contents methodological pedagogical second you parameters Curriculum must to be related to racial ethnic culture and history questions about these in between you contents historical It is O teacher what history It is it is culture afro passed on to our students? Was it just the one on the slave ships? Or extended to our ancestors on the African continent? How did it happen export? What peoples they were these? Like this as to the stories European marked per riches, achievements, traditions, beliefs, songs It is culinary it was our ancestral peoples who had their history marked by devaluation in think that the africa culture It is just the slavery.

With regard to the teaching of African history and culture, the main obstacle to its breakthrough It is broad development concentrate at the unprepared philosophical, sociological,

phenomenological It is epistemological those what they go minister you content to students. Empirical research should take place with as a guiding axis a parallel between the cultural and social unfolding around the Afro-Brazilian culture; how such messages are captured by these students to preparation academic of teacher what minister O teaching he has been truly one mere repetition in all O what he Learned in books written with a view to spreading a distorted and prejudiced idea of Africa, denying your history pre-colonization european, O what contributes greatlyfor to form It is crystallize a view that ever how was it It is presented.

REFERENCES

ARAÚJO, Liliane Rodrigues in; Souza, Sergio Rodrigues in. *A Praxis Pedagogical It is The Culture School Transdisciplinary*. Victory: JRPRINT LTD., 2015.

BRAZIL. *LAW No. 10,639, IN 9 IN JANUARY IN 2003*. Change The Law at the 9,394, in 20 in December in 1996, what lays down to the guidelines It is bases from the education national level, to include in the official curriculum of the Education Network the obligation of thematic “History and Culture Afro-Brazilian”, and from the others arrangements.

BRAZIL. *Law in guidelines It is Bases from the Education National – Law 9394/1996*. Brasilia: print shop of Senate, 1996.

NOTEBOOKS CORNER NAGÔ OF ILÊ AIYÊ. *In: Africa womb fertile of world*. Savior: number SAW, 1988.

FREIRE, Paul. *Pedagogy from the hope : One Reencounter with The Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. São Paulo: Peace It is Earth, 1992.

JACOMELI, Mara Regina Martins. A Law 5,692 in 1971 It is The presence of the Liberal precepts and the New School: Social studies and the formation of citizenship. *In: Magazine HISTORY Online*, Campinas, n.39, P. 76-90, sep.2010. Access on: 25 in November 2016.

PEPPER, S. G. *Training in teachers: Identity It is knowledge from the teaching*. They are Paul: cortez, 1999.